

Effects of Age and Seasonal Variation on Fecal Testosterone Concentrations in Captive Common Palm Civets (*Paradoxurus hermaphroditus*)

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Abstract

The present study investigated the effects of age and seasonal variation on testosterone concentrations in captive common palm civets (*Paradoxurus hermaphroditus*) using a non-invasive endocrine monitoring approach. Fifteen healthy male civets were divided into three age groups, including 12–24 months, 24–36 months, and 36–48 months ($n = 5$ per group). Fecal samples were collected monthly over a 12-month experimental period and analyzed for testosterone metabolites using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). The results demonstrated clear monthly and seasonal fluctuations in testosterone concentrations among age groups. Testosterone levels generally decreased from January to June and increased markedly from September to December. The 24–36 months group consistently exhibited higher testosterone concentrations than the other groups during most months of the study period. Testosterone concentrations ranged from $3.28 \pm 1.63 \mu\text{g/g df}$ to $15.68 \pm 3.80 \mu\text{g/g df}$ throughout the experimental period. Seasonal analysis revealed significantly higher testosterone concentrations during the dry season compared with the rainy season in the 12–24 months and 24–36 months groups ($P < 0.05$). In contrast, no significant seasonal difference was observed in the 36–48 months group. Among all experimental groups, civets aged 24–36 months exhibited the highest average testosterone concentrations during both seasons. The findings indicate that both age and seasonal conditions significantly influence reproductive endocrine activity in captive common palm civets. Fecal testosterone metabolite analysis using ELISA appears to be an effective non-invasive tool for monitoring reproductive physiology in this species. The obtained information may contribute to improving reproductive management, breeding programs, and conservation strategies for captive civet populations.

Keywords: *Common palm civet, ELISA, Paradoxurus hermaphroditus, reproductive physiology, seasonality, testosterone.*

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Introduction

The common palm civet (*Paradoxurus hermaphroditus*) is a small carnivorous mammal widely distributed throughout tropical and subtropical regions of Southeast Asia. In Vietnam, this species is not only ecologically important in forest ecosystems but also possesses economic and conservation value. During recent decades, however, habitat degradation, illegal hunting, and wildlife trade have caused substantial declines in natural populations, increasing the need for effective captive breeding and conservation

management programs. Reproductive performance is considered one of the key factors determining the success of ex situ conservation programs in wildlife species. In captive carnivores, reproductive efficiency is often influenced by environmental conditions, stress, nutritional management, age, and endocrine regulation. Among reproductive hormones, testosterone plays a central role in male reproductive physiology by regulating spermatogenesis, sexual maturation, libido, territorial behavior, and seasonal reproductive activity. Consequently, monitoring testosterone concentrations can provide valuable information regarding reproductive status and breeding potential in captive males.

Traditional blood sampling methods for hormone determination may induce considerable stress responses in wildlife species and can alter endocrine profiles during handling and restraint procedures. For this reason, non-invasive endocrine monitoring techniques based on fecal steroid metabolites have become increasingly important in wildlife reproductive studies. Fecal hormone analysis allows repeated sampling over long periods without disturbing the animals and has been successfully applied in numerous mammalian species, particularly carnivores and endangered wildlife (Palme et al., 2005; Schwarzenberger, 2007). Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) is currently one of the most widely used analytical approaches for fecal steroid monitoring because of its high sensitivity, relatively low cost, and practical applicability under laboratory conditions. Previous studies demonstrated that fecal testosterone metabolites reliably reflect gonadal activity and reproductive status in several carnivore species, including cheetahs, spotted hyenas, and red pandas (Pribbenow et al., 2015; Neema et al., 2016). In male cheetahs, for example, testosterone metabolites increased significantly during the breeding season and showed clear associations with reproductive behavior and testicular activity (Ludwig et al., 2013).

Seasonality is another important factor affecting reproductive endocrine activity in mammals. In many wildlife species, seasonal changes in ambient temperature, rainfall, photoperiod, and food availability can influence hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal function, thereby affecting testosterone secretion patterns. Elevated testosterone concentrations during breeding periods have been documented in numerous carnivores and seasonal breeders (Lincoln et al., 1989). Seasonal endocrine fluctuations are believed to optimize reproductive timing and offspring survival under favorable environmental conditions. In addition to environmental factors, reproductive endocrine activity is strongly influenced by age. Testosterone secretion generally increases during sexual maturation, reaches maximal levels during reproductive adulthood, and subsequently declines with advancing age due to physiological reductions in testicular function. Age-associated endocrine variation has been reported in both domestic and wild mammals and may directly influence fertility and reproductive performance.

Previous studies on common palm civets mainly focused on reproductive biology, captive management, and validation of non-invasive hormone monitoring techniques. Nguyen Thi Thu Hien et al. (2017) described reproductive characteristics of captive civets, while Nguyen Thi Thu Hien et al. (2018) confirmed the applicability of fecal hormone monitoring in this species. Nevertheless, information regarding the combined influence of age and seasonal conditions on testosterone concentrations in captive common palm civets remains limited. Understanding endocrine variation according to age and season may contribute significantly to improving reproductive management strategies, breeding selection, and conservation programs for captive civet populations. Therefore, the present study aimed to evaluate monthly and seasonal variations in fecal testosterone concentrations among different age groups of captive common palm civets using a non-invasive ELISA-based approach.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Animals

Fifteen clinically healthy male common palm civets (*Paradoxurus hermaphroditus*) maintained under captive conditions were included in the experiment. Animals were divided into three age groups:

Group 12–24 months old (2-year-old group, n = 5);

Group 24–36 months old (3-year-old group, n = 5);

Group 36–48 months old (4-year-old group, n = 5).

All civets were housed individually in semi-open cages under similar husbandry and feeding conditions throughout the experimental period. Animals were fed a mixed diet consisting of fruits, commercial feed, and animal protein sources twice daily, with water available *ad libitum*.

Experimental Design and Seasonal Classification

Fecal samples were collected monthly from all experimental animals over a 12-month monitoring period. Based on local climatic conditions in southern Vietnam, the study period was classified into: dry season (December–April) and rainy season (May–November). Monthly testosterone concentrations and seasonal variations were subsequently compared among age groups.

Fecal Sample Collection

Fresh fecal samples were collected immediately after defecation between 18:00 and 20:00 h to minimize environmental degradation of steroid metabolites. Approximately 5 g of feces from each animal was placed into sterile polyethylene bags and transported to the laboratory under refrigerated conditions. Samples were stored at -20°C until hormone extraction and analysis.

Hormone Extraction Procedure

Hormone extraction was performed following modified protocols previously described for wildlife fecal steroid analysis (Wasser et al., 2000; Ziegler & Wittwer, 2005). Briefly, frozen fecal samples were thawed at room temperature and homogenized thoroughly. Approximately 0.2 g of wet fecal material was transferred into a glass tube containing 2 mL of 90% methanol. Samples were vortexed continuously for 30 min using a laboratory shaker to facilitate steroid extraction.

The homogenates were subsequently centrifuged at $1,700 \times g$ for 20 min. The supernatant containing extracted steroid metabolites was collected and transferred into 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tubes. Extracts were stored at -20°C until ELISA analysis. Hormone concentrations were expressed as micrograms per gram of dried feces ($\mu\text{g/g df}$).

ELISA Assay

Fecal testosterone metabolites were quantified using a commercial Testosterone ELISA kit (DRG International Inc., Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Optical density was measured at 450 nm using an automated microplate reader. Standard curves were generated using serial dilutions of testosterone standards ranging from 0.3 to 40 ng/mL. Sample concentrations were calculated based on the corresponding calibration curves. All samples were analyzed in duplicate to minimize analytical variation.

Statistical Analysis

Experimental data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Duncan's multiple range test to compare differences among age groups and seasons. Statistical significance was considered at $P < 0.05$. Results are presented as Mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

Results

Monthly Variation in Testosterone Concentrations According to Age Groups

Monthly testosterone concentrations in captive common palm civets are presented in Table 1. Testosterone levels fluctuated considerably throughout the experimental period and differed among age groups.

Table 1. Monthly Testosterone Concentrations ($\mu\text{g/g df}$) in Common Palm Civets According to Age Groups During the Study Period

Month	2 years old group (n=5) Mean \pm SD	3 years old group (n=5) Mean \pm SD	4 years old group (n=5) Mean \pm SD	MIN	MAX
1	7.25 ^a \pm 1.32	8.76 ^a \pm 1.47	6.94 ^a \pm 1.54	4.84	9.65
2	6.71 ^a \pm 1.73	7.29 ^a \pm 1.46	6.46 ^b \pm 1.65	4.76	9.28
3	6.62 ^a \pm 1.28	7.90 ^b \pm 1.65	6.12 ^b \pm 1.36	3.02	9.74
4	5.31 ^b \pm 1.43	6.74 ^b \pm 1.05	5.88 ^b \pm 0.94	3.88	8.21
5	3.58 ^c \pm 0.97	4.88 ^c \pm 1.15	4.15 ^c \pm 0.82	2.28	8.64
6	3.28 ^c \pm 1.63	4.44 ^c \pm 1.26	4.76 ^c \pm 1.14	2.64	9.02
7	4.56 ^c \pm 1.25	5.51 ^c \pm 1.31	4.28 ^c \pm 1.37	2.45	7.84
8	6.73 ^a \pm 2.11	8.09 ^a \pm 1.95	7.41 ^d \pm 1.05	4.81	11.96
9	9.62 ^d \pm 2.46	11.25 ^d \pm 2.08	10.04 ^e \pm 2.25	6.14	13.42
10	11.95 ^e \pm 2.61	12.51 ^d \pm 1.87	10.73 ^e \pm 2.98	7.36	11.83
11	12.83 ^e \pm 2.28	13.45 ^e \pm 1.59	12.64 ^f \pm 2.65	8.17	16.96
12	14.95 ^f \pm 3.52	15.68 ^e \pm 3.8	13.82 ^f \pm 2.17	8.08	17.31

Note: Values are presented as Mean \pm SD. Different lowercase superscripts within the same column indicate significant differences among months within the same age group ($P < 0.05$). Testosterone concentrations are expressed as micrograms per gram of dried feces ($\mu\text{g/g df}$).

In general, testosterone concentrations tended to decrease gradually from January to June, followed by a marked increase from August onward. The highest concentrations were recorded during the final months of the year, particularly from September to December. Among the experimental groups, civets aged 24–36 months consistently exhibited higher testosterone concentrations than the other age groups during most months of the study period. Testosterone concentrations in this group ranged from $4.44 \pm 1.26 \mu\text{g/g df}$ in June to $15.68 \pm 3.80 \mu\text{g/g df}$ in December.

The 12–24 months group showed comparatively lower testosterone concentrations during the first half of the year, with the lowest value observed in June ($3.28 \pm 1.63 \mu\text{g/g df}$). However, testosterone concentrations increased substantially from September onward, reaching $14.95 \pm 3.52 \mu\text{g/g df}$ in December. Similarly, the 36–48 months group demonstrated seasonal fluctuations in testosterone secretion, although monthly variation appeared less pronounced compared with the younger groups. Testosterone concentrations in this group ranged from $4.15 \pm 0.82 \mu\text{g/g df}$ in May to $13.82 \pm 2.17 \mu\text{g/g df}$ in December.

Statistical analysis revealed significant differences among age groups during several months of the experimental period ($P < 0.05$). The 24–36 months group generally exhibited significantly higher testosterone concentrations than the remaining groups, especially during the reproductive season. Overall, testosterone concentrations increased markedly during the later months of the year, suggesting enhanced reproductive endocrine activity during this period.

Seasonal Variation in Testosterone Concentrations

Seasonal testosterone concentrations according to age groups are summarized in Table 2. The results indicated that testosterone concentrations during the dry season were generally higher than those recorded during the rainy season. In the 12–24 months group, testosterone concentrations averaged $8.17 \pm 3.86 \mu\text{g/g df}$ during the dry season and decreased to $7.51 \pm 3.98 \mu\text{g/g df}$ during the rainy season. A similar trend was observed in the 24–36 months group, where testosterone concentrations were significantly higher during the dry season ($9.27 \pm 3.66 \mu\text{g/g df}$) compared with the rainy season ($8.59 \pm 3.80 \mu\text{g/g df}$) ($P < 0.05$). In contrast, seasonal differences were less pronounced in the 36–48 months group. Testosterone concentrations averaged $7.84 \pm 3.36 \mu\text{g/g df}$ during the dry season and $7.72 \pm 3.47 \mu\text{g/g df}$ during the rainy season, with no statistically significant difference detected between seasons.

Comparison among age groups showed that civets aged 24–36 months maintained significantly higher testosterone concentrations than the other groups during both seasons ($P < 0.05$). Meanwhile, the 12–24 months and 36–48 months groups exhibited relatively similar testosterone concentrations. The observed seasonal pattern demonstrated that testosterone secretion increased during the dry season and toward the end of the year, corresponding to periods associated with elevated reproductive activity.

Table 2. Seasonal Testosterone Concentrations ($\mu\text{g/g df}$) in Common Palm Civets According to Age Groups

Season	2 years old group (n=15) Mean \pm SD	3 years old group (n=15) Mean \pm SD	4 years old group (n=5) Mean \pm SD
Dry season (December–April)	$8.17^{aA} \pm 3.86$	$9.27^{bA} \pm 3.66$	$7.84^{aA} \pm 3.36$
Rainy season (May–November)	$7.51^{aB} \pm 3.98$	$8.59^{bB} \pm 3.80$	$7.72^{aA} \pm 3.47$
Average	7.78 ± 3.76	8.88 ± 3.59	7.77 ± 3.27

Note: Different lowercase superscripts within the same row indicate significant differences among age groups ($P < 0.05$). Different uppercase superscripts within the same column indicate significant differences between seasons within the same age group ($P < 0.05$).

Discussion

The present study demonstrated that testosterone concentrations in captive common palm civets varied considerably according to both age and seasonal conditions. Monthly testosterone profiles revealed a clear decline during the middle months of the year, followed by a marked increase from September to December. This pattern suggests that reproductive endocrine activity in captive common palm civets may exhibit a distinct seasonal tendency, even under captive management conditions. Seasonal fluctuations in testosterone secretion have been widely documented in mammals, particularly in carnivores and seasonal breeders. Testosterone production is regulated primarily through the hypothalamic–pituitary–gonadal axis and is strongly influenced by environmental factors such as photoperiod, temperature, rainfall, and food availability (Lincoln et al., 2006). In many wildlife species, reproductive endocrine activity increases during periods that maximize mating success and offspring survival under favorable environmental conditions.

In the present study, testosterone concentrations during the dry season were generally higher than those observed during the rainy season, particularly in the younger age groups. This finding may indicate that environmental conditions during the dry season favor reproductive activation in captive common palm civets. Similar seasonal endocrine patterns have been reported in several carnivore species. Neema et al. (2016) observed significant seasonal variation in fecal reproductive hormone metabolites in red pandas,

where androgen concentrations increased during the breeding season. Likewise, Pribbenow et al. (2015) reported elevated fecal androgen metabolite concentrations during periods of reproductive activity in spotted hyenas. The marked increase in testosterone concentrations from September onward observed in the present study may correspond to enhanced gonadal activity and reproductive readiness. In tropical mammals, seasonal endocrine responses are often less pronounced than those observed in temperate species; however, environmental fluctuations may still modulate reproductive physiology through endocrine signaling pathways (Palme et al., 2005). Seasonal changes in rainfall and ambient temperature may indirectly influence metabolic activity, nutritional status, and reproductive behavior, thereby affecting testosterone secretion patterns.

Age-related variation in testosterone concentrations was another important finding of the present study. Civets aged 24–36 months consistently exhibited higher testosterone concentrations compared with the younger and older groups during most months of the experimental period. This result suggests that animals within this age range may represent the peak reproductive stage in male common palm civets.

The relatively lower testosterone concentrations observed in the 12–24 months group may reflect incomplete reproductive maturation. Testosterone secretion generally increases progressively during puberty and early adulthood due to enhanced Leydig cell activity and maturation of the reproductive endocrine system. Similar age-associated increases in testosterone concentrations have been reported in several mammalian species, including carnivores and primates (Lincoln et al., 2006). Interestingly, the oldest group (36–48 months) exhibited comparatively lower testosterone concentrations and less pronounced seasonal variation than the 24–36 months group. Although these animals remained reproductively active, the reduced endocrine fluctuation may suggest early age-associated declines in testicular endocrine responsiveness. Age-related reductions in androgen production have previously been associated with decreased spermatogenic activity, reduced reproductive performance, and alterations in gonadal physiology in mammals.

The present findings are generally consistent with previous reproductive studies conducted in common palm civets. Nguyen Thi Thu Hien et al. (2017) reported reproductive characteristics and breeding patterns in captive civets, while Nguyen Thi Thu Hien et al. (2018) demonstrated the applicability of fecal steroid monitoring as a non-invasive approach for evaluating reproductive hormones in this species. The current study extends previous findings by providing additional evidence regarding the combined effects of age and seasonal conditions on testosterone secretion patterns. Non-invasive endocrine monitoring has become increasingly important in wildlife reproductive management because conventional blood sampling procedures may induce substantial stress responses and potentially alter hormone concentrations during handling and restraint (Touma & Palme, 2005). Fecal steroid analysis offers several advantages, including reduced animal disturbance, repeated long-term sampling capability, and improved applicability under captive and conservation conditions (Schwarzenberger, 2007).

The ELISA-based method used in the present study proved suitable for monitoring testosterone metabolites in common palm civets. Similar approaches have been successfully applied in several wildlife species, including cheetahs, brown hyenas, and roe deer (Dehnhard et al., 2001; Hulsman et al., 2011). According to Wasser et al. (2000), fecal steroid metabolite analysis represents one of the most practical tools for long-term endocrine assessment in wildlife conservation programs. The findings obtained in the present study may provide useful baseline information for captive breeding management of common palm civets. Identification of periods associated with elevated testosterone concentrations may assist breeding facilities in optimizing pairing strategies, reproductive timing, and male selection for breeding programs. Furthermore, understanding age-associated endocrine variation may contribute to improved reproductive management and conservation planning for captive populations.

Nevertheless, several limitations should be considered. The number of experimental animals was relatively limited, and additional studies involving larger populations and complementary reproductive

parameters such as semen quality or behavioral observations would provide a more comprehensive understanding of reproductive physiology in this species. Future studies may also investigate the relationships among testosterone concentrations, stress hormones, and reproductive success under different captive management conditions. The present study contributes additional information regarding reproductive endocrinology in common palm civets and highlights the important influence of age and seasonal conditions on testosterone secretion patterns in captive males.

Conclusion

The present study demonstrated that testosterone concentrations in captive common palm civets varied significantly according to both age and seasonal conditions. Monthly testosterone concentrations decreased during the middle months of the year and increased markedly toward the end of the year, particularly from September to December, indicating seasonal reproductive endocrine activity. Among the experimental groups, civets aged 24–36 months consistently exhibited the highest testosterone concentrations, suggesting that this age range may represent the peak reproductive stage in male common palm civets. Seasonal comparison further revealed that testosterone concentrations during the dry season were significantly higher than those observed during the rainy season in the younger age groups. The study also confirmed that fecal testosterone metabolite analysis using ELISA is a practical and reliable non-invasive method for monitoring reproductive endocrine function in captive civets. This approach may provide valuable information for reproductive management, breeding selection, and conservation programs. The present findings contribute additional knowledge regarding reproductive endocrinology in common palm civets and provide useful baseline data for future reproductive and conservation studies in this species.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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